

Do science maps from open access literature capture the overall topic structure of an academic field?

A study on sustainable food research

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This study compares the science map of sustainable food research constructed using only open access (OA) publications to that using all papers. Citation network analysis revealed 17 and 15 clusters in the OA and full datasets, respectively, with good correspondence between the two at the cluster level. However, at the subcluster level, several specific topics present in the full network were absent from the OA representation. The results suggest that while OA science maps capture broad research trends, they may miss granular subtopics. This has implications for researchers relying solely on OA data for scientific mapping.

1. Introduction

Academia has been undergoing a gradual transition from a predominantly subscription-based system to an open access model (Piwowar et al., 2018). This shift towards open science has been driven by various mandates, trends, and evolving publication business models, which have collectively contributed to making research more accessible and transparent (Greussing et al., 2020). The progress towards openness has become increasingly noticeable in recent years, with a growing number of publications being made freely available to readers worldwide.

The increase in open access publications may lead researchers to assume that focusing solely on openly available papers for scientific mapping and analysis would be sufficient to capture overall research trends. In this direction, this study aims to investigate the differences between science maps constructed using all papers on a given topic and those created using only open access papers. By comparing the knowledge structures that emerge from these two approaches, we seek to understand the persistence of key themes and identify any significant topics or trends that may be overlooked when relying exclusively on open access publications. Through this analysis, we hope to shed light on the potential limitations and biases that may arise from focusing solely on open access content in scientific mapping endeavors.

The adoption of open access practices varies significantly across different fields of study (Antelman, 2004; Moon et al., 2007; Walters & Linvill, 2011). Some disciplines, such as Computer Science, have been at the forefront of the open access movement, embracing preprint servers and open repositories more readily than others. In contrast, certain fields, like Medicine and Chemistry, have been slower to adopt open access publishing, often due to long-standing publishing traditions and concerns regarding intellectual property rights. Consequently, the extent of openness in academic publishing cannot be generalized across all disciplines.

In this study we focus on sustainable food research which we believe is a particularly suitable target due to its multidisciplinary nature (Dekker et al., 2020; Francis et al., 2008), coverage of open access literature, societal relevance, and diverse funding landscape (Letty et al., 2022). As a field that spans multiple disciplines, sustainable food systems research attracts contributions from researchers with potentially varied publication practices and open access adoption rates. Its average open access coverage positions it as a representative case study for understanding

the dynamics between open access and non-open access publications. The societal relevance of sustainable food systems research, and the influence of funder mandates on open access adoption make it an interesting lens through which to examine how publishing practices intersect with research priorities, knowledge sharing, and scholarly communication. Studying this field can provide nuanced insights into the role and impact of open access in a specific research domain, informing broader discussions on open access trends in academia.

2. Data and Methods

To explore the science maps of sustainable food research we first need to gather data from bibliographic databases. We downloaded bibliographic records from the Web of Science (WoS) Core Collection which is one of the commonly used databases for bibliometric analysis. WoS indexes articles across all domains of science and offers well-formatted data mostly ready for programmatic processing. Articles in WoS are also labelled by their OA types. WoS sources this information from OurResearch a non-profit organization providing OA database content (Clarivate, 2024). The types of OA included in WOS are Gold, Hybrid, Bronze (Free to Read) which refer to public access to the final peer-reviewed version directly from the publisher platform. Additionally, we find Green Published, Green Accepted, and Green Submitted referring to articles available through repositories. To extract the articles we conducted a topical search using the query `TS=("sustainab*" NEAR/2 "food*")` to look for articles matching those keywords in the title, abstract, or keyword fields. The asterisk allows getting multiple inflections of the same keyword (e.g. sustainable, sustainability) and the NEAR operator enables matches when the keywords are separated by up to 2 intermediate words (e.g. sustainable access to food) making the search comprehensive. We search for any type of document over all the years available in the database. We found 12,750 documents by the time of retrieval on April 1 2024.

The science map representing the knowledge structure of sustainable food research was made following the steps outlined in Figure 1. We copied the subset of open access articles as a separate dataset, so we have two inputs, one dataset with all documents, and one with open access documents only. Then we computed the following steps in both datasets independently. We created a direct citation network (Boyack & Klavans, 2010; de Solla Price, 1965) and retained the largest component as orphan papers or clusters that do not cite or are not cited by the other articles in the dataset may imply keyword matches from papers that do not belong to the main corpus of research. Then, we clustered the networks using a network community detection algorithm (Blondel et al., 2008). Science maps created in this manner have been found useful for detecting emerging research fronts (Shibata et al., 2008) and capturing the backbone of science (Boyack et al., 2011). Summary statistics for each cluster were computed, including average citations and publication years of the articles in the cluster. We also summarized the proportion of articles mentioning the keyword “policy” in the title, abstract, or keywords to have a proxy indicator of policy interest across the clusters. Finally, we compared the OA network with the full network by finding the distribution of the documents that compose the OA clusters inside the clusters of the full network clusters.

Figure 1. Overview of the methodology

The implementation of the network and data analysis was made using the R statistical software (R Core Team, 2019), mainly relying in the package Igraph (Csárdi et al., 2024), while the networks were plot using Gephi (Bastian et al., 2009).

3. Results

The dataset in the largest component consists of 8,528 documents published since 1986 with 5,309 (62.3%) of them being classified as OA. Figure 2 presents the yearly publication trend. The number of publications in sustainable food systems research has been steadily increasing year over year, indicating a growing interest in this field. The same can be said when focusing on OA publications. In the past 10 years we see an increase in the proportion of OA publications from 42% in 2015 to a 72% in 2021, being 60% the yearly average.

Figure 2. Yearly publication trend.

The growing trend in OA publications is accompanied by a shift in the type of OA. Figure 3 shows the yearly trend by different types of OA. Gold and Green Published have been the dominant types, with the hybrid type of publications showing an increase over time.

Figure 3. Types of OA publications over time.

The knowledge structure is revealed through a science map based on citation networks. Two networks were built representing the structure for all articles and for OA articles only, as shown in Figure 4. Each cluster is represented by different colors (given that the networks were developed independently, the colors between the two are unrelated and do not necessarily signify the same topic). Network (a) contains 15 clusters and (b), despite being of smaller size, contains 17 which is a result of the network also being sparser. Each cluster was named based on the contents of the most connected and more cited articles that compose them. Tables 1 and 2 summarize the clusters' statistics.

Figure 4. Science maps of Sustainable Food research for (a) all articles and (b) OA articles only.

Table 1. Cluster statistics for the network with all documents.

<i>Cl.</i>	<i>Topic</i>	<i>Articles</i>	<i>Ave. Year</i>	<i>Ave. Cites</i>	<i>OA articles</i>	<i>Policy articles</i>
1	Agri-food and agroecology	1298	2,018.5	24.6	62.9%	34.3%
2	Sustainable food consumption and diets	1182	2,020.8	27.6	73.9%	36.2%
3	Innovation in sustainable food	1172	2,019.1	55.9	58.5%	26.5%
4	Promoting Sustainable Food Consumption	905	2,020.0	27.0	59.6%	24.9%
5	Alternative foods	771	2,020.8	30.3	65.8%	9.5%
6	Waste management and Circular Economy	659	2,020.6	27.2	62.4%	22.9%
7	Sustainable packaging	611	2,021.2	29.6	53.5%	9.0%
8	Supply Chain Optimization	553	2,019.7	31.7	53.9%	23.3%
9	Urban agriculture	366	2,019.9	26.2	64.2%	22.4%
10	Nano and biotechnology	266	2,020.8	59.6	53.4%	9.8%
11	Traditional Agricultural Methods	226	2,019.6	29.9	69.5%	27.9%
12	Public access to food	162	2,018.2	17.5	65.4%	43.2%
13	Water Usage	159	2,018.8	30.8	50.9%	37.1%
14	Technology Management	105	2,020.8	31.7	71.4%	45.7%
15	Others	93	2,021.4	16.0	60.2%	20.4%

When considering all articles, the largest cluster by number of publications is dedicated to food production in the context of agri-food and agroecology which is also a matured one being the second oldest by average publication year. Sustainable packaging and alternative foods (e.g. plant-based meats) are the newest trends. Nano and biotechnology research, and the topic of innovation are the most relevant in terms of the average citations. The topics of sustainable food and technology management are those with largest concentrations of OA articles, and technology management and public access to food are those with larger concentration of policy-related papers.

We then compared the clusters of the OA network with the full network. Figure 5 shows a heatmap of the concentration of articles for each pair of clusters. The figure is meant to be read row-wise signaling the presence of papers from each OA clusters in the full network clusters. For example, 91% of articles in OA cluster 13 appear inside cluster 5 of the full network, this being the largest intersection in the heatmap. In table 2, we label with a check mark (✓) each OA cluster having a high topical correspondence to a full network cluster, and with diamond (◆) those clusters with high concentration of articles but that are more topically specific than the full cluster topic they match. This assessment is done qualitatively after checking the clusters contents.

Figure 5. OA clusters concentration within the full network clusters

Table 2. Cluster statistics for the network of OA documents.

<i>Cl.</i>	<i>Topic</i>	<i>Articles</i>	<i>Ave. Year</i>	<i>Ave. Cites</i>	<i>Policy articles</i>
1	Sustainable food consumption and diets ✓	701	2,020.5	29.6	35.5%
2	Food Security ◆	610	2,020.2	59.5	28.0%
3	Sustainability transitions ◆	586	2,020.7	22.1	45.6%
4	Promoting Sustainable Food Consumption ✓	443	2,021.0	24.6	24.4%
5	Alternative foods ✓	383	2,021.2	30.2	13.6%
6	Food Waste and Circular Economy ✓	362	2,020.8	28.3	24.0%
7	Sustainable supply chains ◆	301	2,020.1	19.4	32.6%

<i>Cl.</i>	<i>Topic</i>	<i>Articles</i>	<i>Ave. Year</i>	<i>Ave. Cites</i>	<i>Policy articles</i>
8	Urban agriculture ✓	193	2,020.4	24.4	24.9%
9	Nano and biotechnology ♦	152	2,020.7	60.4	7.9%
10	Sustainable Packaging ✓	145	2,021.1	25.6	13.1%
11	Traditional agriculture and local methods ✓	144	2,020.5	31.5	29.9%
12	Food supply disruptions	129	2,021.5	28.4	28.7%
13	Alternative foods: insects ✓	128	2,021.5	27.4	7.0%
14	Aquaculture	119	2,020.8	23.6	45.4%
15	Food processing and byproducts	111	2,021.0	31.4	18.9%
16	Public food consumption ♦	90	2,020.0	12.9	37.8%
17	Others	205	2,020.9	44.2	24.4%

We observed that cluster 13 (Water usage) and 14 (technology management) in the full network are not represented in the OA network. Conversely, The OA cluster of supply chain disruptions, aquaculture, and food processing and byproducts are diluted across the full network clusters.

It can be argued that the clusters in the full network are big enough to absorb OA clusters. An example of this is that the cluster 5 (Alternative food) in the full network capture a large proportion of articles of clusters 5 and 13 of the OA network, these also being on alternative foods, one more generic and the other focused on insect protein consumption research. Thus, we performed a subclustering step to find clusters that are more specific in meaning. The subclustering is done by taking each cluster’ network representation and apply the community detection algorithm on it. We obtained 79 and 37 subclusters respectively, and the matching is shown in Figure 6. At the granular level, is more apparent that several specific topics from the full network are not represented in the OA network, which is observed by the columns that are mostly blank in the figure.

Figure 6. OA subclusters concentration within the full network subclusters

4. Discussion and conclusion

The increasing prevalence of open access (OA) publications in academic research may raise questions about the representativeness of science maps based solely on OA data compared to those constructed using all available papers. In this study, we compared citation networks of food system research using both OA papers and the complete set of papers to investigate the differences and similarities between the resulting science maps.

Our analysis revealed that the network constructed using all papers had 15 clusters, while the OA paper network had 17 clusters. Interestingly, we found a good correspondence between the two networks at the cluster level, with 8 OA clusters being semantically similar to clusters in the full network, 5 OA clusters being relatively similar, and only 4 clusters showing significant differences.

This finding addresses two contrasting perspectives on the use of OA data for science mapping. Some researchers may believe that the growing number of OA publications is sufficient to represent a research field comprehensively (e.g., Quille et al., 2023; Thiabaud et al., 2020). Conversely, It may be argued that OA science maps will always differ from complete science maps due to the structural differences in the citation networks and the non-random distribution of OA research. Our study highlights the importance of examining the actual correspondence between OA and complete science maps to assess the validity of these assumptions.

Despite the differences observed, our results suggest that OA science maps can capture larger research trends, even if they may not provide comprehensive coverage. This is evidenced by the relevant overlap between the two maps at the cluster level. However, at the subcluster level, we found that while many OA subclusters matched those in the full network, several subclusters present in the full network were absent from the OA representation.

These findings serve as a cautionary tale for researchers relying solely on OA data for scientific mapping. While OA science maps can effectively capture broad research trends, they may miss granular, specific subtopics that could be critical in fields such as research front detection (Rotolo et al., 2015; Shibata et al., 2008). Researchers should be aware of these limitations when interpreting results based on OA data alone.

Our study makes contributions to both sustainable food research and the bibliometric community. By revealing the main trends in food system research, we provide insights on the main trends, OA coverage, and policy interest across the diverse topics that compose the field. Moreover, our comparison of OA and full data science maps contributes to the ongoing discussion on the representativeness of OA data in bibliometric analyses.

Although this being an exploratory study based on a single research field, the results made us hypothesize the existence of a 'threshold of topical convergence,' a point at which OA data becomes sufficient to properly represent a full topic, even if a proportion of publications remain paywalled. This concept presents an opportunity for future research, as identifying such a threshold could have significant implications for the use of OA data in science mapping, in the sense that for fields reaching such a threshold researchers may comfortably disregard expensive databases.

We acknowledge the limitations of our study. As a single case study focused on sustainable food research, our findings may not be generalizable to other research fields. Additionally,

future studies could explore text-based clustering techniques to further investigate the commonalities and differences between OA and full data science maps.

In conclusion, our study demonstrates that while OA science maps can capture larger research trends, they may miss specific subtopics that could be critical in certain fields. Researchers should exercise caution when relying solely on OA data for scientific mapping and consider the potential limitations of their analyses. As the proportion of OA publications continues to grow, further research is needed to explore the concept of a 'threshold of topical convergence' and its implications for bibliometric studies.

Open science practices

Data used in this article was sourced from the Web of Science by utilizing the query specified in the Data and Methods section. An equivalent dataset containing relevant fields (e.g., Title, DOI) has been made available using OpenAlex data and stored in Zenodo. 10.5281/zenodo.11047499

Partial code associated with the data processing is available in the same link.

Competing interests

No competing interests.

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